

Community Empowerment through New Entrepreneurship in the Era of the Corona Virus Pandemic in Banten Province

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ABSTRACT: The Corona Virus pandemic that has hit almost all countries, including Indonesia, especially in the province of Banten, which is part of Indonesia, is geographically located to the west of the national capital, namely Jakarta, with a distance of approximately two hours away, with a population of 11,904.562 people, which became the location of the research which was held in 2021, with research samples taken randomly as many as 311 respondents with characteristics as lower middle class people who live in cities and districts in Banten province as the main data source.

On this basis, research that uses a qualitative descriptive analysis approach coupled with descriptive statistical analysis methods as reinforcement in interpreting research results that aims to answer the focus or research problem regarding, "*Community Empowerment Through New Entrepreneurship in the Corona Virus Pandemic Era in Banten Province, Indonesia.*"

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be stated that; 1) the implications of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the empowerment and powerlessness of the Banten people in the form of, a) 0.11 percent lost their jobs, b) 0.14 percent of workers were laid off or terminated, c) 0.68 percent experienced a reduction or loss of income, d) as much as 0.07 percent of the people actually experienced an increase in income, which is a little hopeful condition even in the midst of the Corona emergency, but there is still a glimmer of hope that the people actually increase their income. 2) the existence of community empowerment activities through new entrepreneurship in the era of the Covid-19 Pandemic in the province of Banten in the form of; a) opening 0.16 percent of new entrepreneurship in the culinary sector, b) opening up new entrepreneurship in the field of buying and selling goods based on digital networks as much as 0.11 percent, and c) opening new entrepreneurship in the field of buying and selling basic needs of the community as much as 0.09 percent.

This research, convincingly has been able to leverage that, the Corona Pandemic not only limits people's activities and causes people's powerlessness, but on the other hand the Corona Pandemic can also awaken the community's fighting power to be able to rise by taking advantage of strategic opportunities in the form of opening various new entrepreneurships that can be used as a catalyst and new energy as a source of new awakening for the growth of the community's economy, both during the Corona Pandemic and post-Corona Pandemic later.

KEY WORDS: Community Empowerment

INTRODUCTION

Community empowerment programs in Indonesia have begun to develop rapidly since 1990, which is used as one of the strategic approaches in sustainable development in all fields, because by including and empowering in development activities, it means that the community will be directly involved and play an active role in development activities both at home and abroad, urban and in rural areas.

Empowering the community is a noble activity, because community empowerment activities are expected to raise the dignity of the community it self, where the weak community can develop the ability to live independently and side by side with a strong community, while a strong community is expected to help weak communities to thrive can live prosperously and independently. However, in community empowerment, it is necessary to observe and pay attention to the background and characteristics of the community itself, in order to be able to follow and adapt to the process of changing times which fluctuates so quickly and sometimes it is difficult to follow, especially changes in so aspects of communication and information technology that are so fast and powerful. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare the community so that they have capabilities that can be used as capital to be more empowered.

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According to Sulistiyani (2004:7), it is explained that, etymologically, empowerment comes from the word power which means strength or ability, thus empowerment can be interpreted as a process to obtain power or provide power to groups of people who are not empowered, especially when the country is experiencing a COVID-19 emergency, which started from Wuhan, China at the end of 2019, and spread massively to all countries in the world, which ultimately made the Corona virus a global pandemic, which limited human activity and mobility within and between countries.

Especially in Indonesia, the first case of Covid-19 occurred in March 2020, which subsequently spread so quickly throughout Indonesia, on this basis the activities and mobility of the community have been limited by various government policies aimed at controlling the spread of Corona to various levels of society, according to data from the Central Bureau of Statistics in 2021 stated that there were 19.1 million people (9.3 percent) of the working age population who were affected by the Corona Pandemic in the form of job losses and loss of income.

The most serious impact that is felt by the community as a result of the Corona Pandemic is a direct impact on the level of community empowerment such as workers who lose their jobs, so this causes people's income to decrease, and causes a decline in people's purchasing power and ultimately decreases the level of community welfare in generally.

This condition is caused by many factors, one of which is the existence of government policies in the form of limiting and reducing the mobility of people out of the house, by making policies to work and do business from home, school from home, which in the end results in a decrease in productivity, especially in the product sector and services.

Therefore, this study tries to examine the empirical conditions that are intended to answer the research questions, namely; *"How is community empowerment through the new Entrepreneurship Era of the Corona Virus Pandemic in Banten Province?."*

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Empowerment emphasizes that a person acquires sufficient skills, knowledge, and power to become capital in his life. According to Parson (Edi Suharti, 2006: 58), empowerment activities can be in the form of providing skills training, providing assistance, providing assistance, and other activities according to community needs. Meanwhile, according to Mardikanto, community empowerment is an effort to make the community independent, this effort can be interpreted as the ability of individuals to integrate with the community as an effort to build an empowered and effective society.

Edi Suharto, (2006:60), explains that community empowerment can be interpreted as a process and as a goal, where community empowerment can be carried out through stages, namely; 1) community empowerment as a process; is a series of activities to strengthen weak community groups so that they are free from various disabilities, 2) community empowerment as a goal ;is a condition to be achieved either through social change that can make the community more empowered by having the knowledge and ability to be able to meet various needs of life better in the economic sector or in social life in general such as having self-confidence, being able to express aspirations, having a livelihood and able to play an active role in social life and be independent in various life tasks.

Furthermore, according to Mardikanto, there are several objectives of community empowerment, namely; 1) institutional improvement; is a process to increase institutional capacity through system improvement and business partnership network development, 2) business improvement; is a community empowerment is expected to have good implications for business improvement, by improving the qualifications and quality of education by increasing the enthusiasm for learning, as well as by participating in or by providing life skill training, 3) improving income or income; this is the most strategic thing in community empowerment is the creation of an improvement in the income of the community itself, by expanding the reach of business which includes multi-sector marketing based on digital networks including the use of social media, 4) environmental improvement; along with the improvement in income and education, it is expected to improve environmental conditions, both the physical environment, the social environment and the economic environment as a result of which people's lives become more empowered and more prosperous, 5) improve the status of life; after the creation of an improvement in the level of life which is supported by an improvement in the environment and income, it is hoped that the community can improve the degree of every family life in the form of increasing purchasing power of the community or family, as well as increasing the strata of social life of the community itself, 6) the realization of a better community life; as an implication of improving and improving the quality of education accompanied by the possession of competencies relevant to the advancement of science and technology.

In order for the purpose of community empowerment to be achieved properly, it is necessary to pay attention to several principles as according to Edi Suharto, (2006:68), there are several principles that must be considered, 1) empowerment is a collaborative process, 2) it is the community as the main actor who must be empowered, 3) utilizing a multi-sector network, 4)

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must be accompanied by a high awareness to be more empowered, 5) must participate actively in every activity, 6) the empowerment process must be dynamic, synergistic and sustainable, 7) empowerment must be evaluation.

In order to achieve empowerment goals as expected, appropriate empowerment strategies are needed as proposed by Parson 1994:112, (Edi Suharto, 2006:66), there are three main strategies, namely; 1) micro strategy; this empowerment strategy is prioritized for individual level empowerment through guidance activities, 2) mezzo strategy; this strategy is implemented for empowerment activities at the group level in the form of activities such as skills training and group dynamics, 3) macro strategy; this strategy is intended for empowerment activities at the wider community level, with activities for making social action plans, social policies, community organizing. The community empowerment strategy is essentially a movement from, by and for the community, which means that the community is active in planning programs, implementing programs, overseeing programs and assessing the success of empowerment programs that are tailored to the potential and needs of the community itself, Suyono, H (2014: 89).

According to Fahrudin, (2012: 96), community empowerment can be in the form of providing the ability or empowering the community to have the ability and independence that can be done by going through the stages, namely; 1) enabling; at this stage community empowerment in the form of creating a climate atmosphere that provides opportunities for the potential possessed by the community to grow and develop continuously, which in the end the community is expected to motivate and raise self-awareness of their own and sustainable potential in order to develop themselves to be more empowered productively, 2) empowering; at this stage the community's capacity and potential are increased so that they have a wider ability to open and establish and utilize multiple accesses in order to take advantage of opportunities that can make the community more prosperous, 3) protection; at this stage the empowerment activity is to provide protection so that the community feels safe and comfortable in their activities and business, namely the community is free from all unfair competition, free from exploitation from strong groups, free from discrimination or oppression from strong groups.

However, community empowerment must pay attention to the values that are inherent in society such as the value of goodness and truth, the value of togetherness, sincerity, mutual cooperation, honesty, hard work, must be built and maintained in order to create change in order to obtain a more empowered life, and more prosperous. This is in line with the opinion of Abbot, (1996:16), which states that community development needs to pay attention to and respect and uphold the values of equality, justice, and togetherness, these values are intended to be a filter from the emergence of social jealousy, and most fundamentally to avoid social jealousy of discrimination in social life.

The community empowerment program is expected to foster the spirit and ability of the community to be able to compete in the global era, therefore the community empowerment process must be carried out in a targeted, timely and efficient manner with various forms of strategic programs such as; 1) community empowerment in the economic sector, this economic empowerment program is classified as a program that has a central and very strategic role, because this program is expected to be able to make people live independently and prosperously, strategic programs such as the development of small and medium enterprises that provide assistance to the community in business such as batik, choliner business, savings and loan cooperatives and digital-based small economic businesses, 2) community empowerment programs in agriculture, by utilizing agricultural land to be managed and planted with various productive crops, such as rice, peanuts, corn, vegetables. Vegetables, the results of which are not only used for family consumption, but can also be distributed or sold to traditional markets or modern markets as a source of income or additional family income, then to UN increase the quantity and quality of agricultural production, farming communities are given training about farming good and productive, so that in the end the farming community will be more productive and live prosperously, 3) community empowerment program in the health sector, with this program the community is expected to be able to improve their quality of life and care more about their own health by prioritizing health promotion and disease prevention programs, health treatment and rehabilitation, as well as providing various trainings on environmental management and healthy personal hygiene. and independence in determining the assistance of health workers when needed, 4) community empowerment programs in the field of education, education is a very strategic part in becoming a smart person, that's why education must be felt and can be achieved by all levels of society both in cities and in rural areas. Education is important because through education the community will be able to develop themselves to be literate in information and communication technology that is tailored to the needs and keeps up with the times, 5) community empowerment in the field of religion, community empowerment programs in the field of religion are needed, because people can be proud of their children is smart in academics, but what is the meaning if it is not accompanied by a religious appearance, which can always display the best and commendable behavior of all time.

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In the end, empowering the community can be seen from various indicators such as; 1) the community has freedom in self-mobility, 2) the community has the ability to meet basic needs, 3) is able to obtain greater clothing and food, 4) is active in various social planning and decisions, 5) has legal and political awareness, 6) have a good and productive economic status and live a prosperous life.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research uses a naturalistic descriptive qualitative method, where the qualitative research results are a description of the observations of the nouns that are currently happening. Therefore, the validity and objectivity of the results are largely determined by the strength of the words and sentences described (Moleong, 2007). In this study, the researchers collected data from the main data source as many as 311 people.

Respondents, while the researcher acts as a human instrument, to obtain data to answer the research objectives, the researcher uses interview and observation guidelines and open questionnaires as an objective guide in data processing and analysis.

The data collection process was carried out qualitatively, namely through stages; 1) orientation stage; at this stage detailed observations are made in order to get an overview of data sources and research locations, 2) exploration stage; at this stage real data collection activities are carried out using interview guidelines and observation guidelines and distributing questionnaires to be studied the contents of the data respondents were 311 people, 3) the triangulation stage; at this stage the researcher re-checked the data obtained, by confirming to a third party who understood and knew about the truth of the data obtained.

Then for qualitative data analysis the researcher used interactive analysis techniques with the Miles and Huberman model (A. Muri Yusuf, 2013 p. 410), which includes the following stages: 1) the reduction stage; at this stage the researcher sorts and selects the data according to the research focus that the researcher formulates, 2) the display stage; at this stage the data that the researcher has collected are compiled in a narrative formulation that already has meaning in order to answer the research focus, and stage 3) the verification stage; at this stage the researcher formulates a provisional conclusion, to be clearer following the visualization of the interactive analysis model as shown below.

RESEARCH OF RESULTS

Based on the results of data processing and analysis obtained from interviews and observations as well as from the results of the analysis of the questionnaire answers from 311 respondents, both the results of descriptive qualitative analysis, and the results of descriptive statistical analysis using a simple formula, namely the mean formula, it can be stated that research results that aim to answer research problems that are in accordance with the research focus, namely; *"Community Empowerment Through New Entrepreneurship in the Era of the Corona Virus Pandemic in Banten Province, Indonesia."*

Based on the results of research data analysis aimed at answering two sub-problems, it can be stated that; 1) the implications of the Corona virus pandemic on the empowerment and powerlessness of the Banten people, there are several forms including; a) as many as 0,11 percent (low category), who experienced job loss, b) as many as 0,14 percent of workers (less category), who were at home or dismissed from work, c) as many as 0,68 percent of the community experienced a reduction or lost income and, d) as much as 0,07 percent (very low category) people actually experienced an increase in income. This condition shows that, in the midst of difficulties and the crush of the Corona Pandemic, it turns out that there is still encouraging hope where people remain optimistic and try to rise from the difficulties they face, 2) there are community empowerment activities through new entrepreneurship in the Corona pandemic era in Banten Province, in the form of; a) opening new entrepreneurship in the culinary business sector as much as 0,16 percent (small category), b) opening new entrepreneurship in the digital network-based trading business as much as 0,11 percent (small category) and, c) opening new entrepreneurship in the buying and selling business basic needs as much as 0.09 percent (very few categories), for this reason the following visualization of research results is as shown in the following table.

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Table. Community Empowerment Through New Entrepreneurship in the Era of the Corona Virus Pandemic in Banten Province Indonesia

N0	Aspect Under Study	Type	Amount	Percent	Average Percent
1	Community empowerment and powerlessness in the form of job and income loss	Loss of a job	33	0,11	0,25
		Status of workers who are at home	43	0,14	
		Loss and decrease in income	213	0,68	
		An increase in peoples income	22	0,07	
2	Community empowerment by opening new entrepreneurship (0,12)	Food entrepreneur	49	0,16	0,12
		Buy and sell online	33	0,11	
		Buying and selling basic necessities	31	0,09	
	Respondents		311		

Sources of questionnaire answers from 311 respondents

Based on Banten population data, there are still as many as 0,11 percent of working age who are not working or unemployed, and as many as 0,08 percent of the population who are poor, (Banten Province Statistics Bureau 2021), if this is compared with the results of this study, the level of error of 0,03-0,05 percent, can be declared quite valid.

The interpretation of the research results is that the Corona Pandemic has a broad impact on people's lives, and has caused changes in all aspects of the order of life, this does not only occur in developing countries such as Indonesia but also in almost all developed countries in the world, all of its people experience suffering. This suffering occurs as a result of various government policies in controlling the Corona virus, whose programs are almost the same in all countries, namely in the form of limiting people's activities and mobility not to leave their homes, even though the economic demands in the Corona Pandemic era are getting heavier and this is getting worse. Exacerbated because people can not work or try optimally outside the home. However, with all the power and effort by taking advantage of the various possible opportunities that exist, the community is still trying to rise from adversity and helplessness, namely, by using opportunities as capital to achieve success and rise from adversity by trying to open new entrepreneurship.'

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study it can be concluded that; Community empowerment through new entrepreneurship in the Corona Pandemic era in Banten, it can be concluded that a small portion of the community can open new entrepreneurship, such as in the culinary business, buying and selling digitally, and in the form of buying and selling materials and other basic needs.

The empowerment of the community in taking advantage of opportunities amid the threat of the Corona virus should be proud, because this proves that the community is still capable and has the courage and independence to rise from adversity and helplessness as an implication of the ferocious and massive spread of the Corona virus so that it has implications for the empowerment and powerlessness of the community, especially the people of Banten in the form of losing their jobs as a result of workers being laid off or laid off from their jobs, there are also people who experience reduced or even lost income, however, there are also among the people who actually experience an increase in income, as well as the efforts and efforts of the community to remain empowered in the form of various new business activities such as, opening a new business in the culinary field, opening a new business in the field of digital-based trading and opening a new business in the field of buying and selling other basic necessities.

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